

OPTIMAL DESIGN OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE PLATES AND BUCKLING TEST

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the experimental results through buckling test of 300 composite rectangular plates coincide with theoretical analysis. The selections of optimal content of matrix and optimal off-axis which make fiber reinforced composite plates reach biggest critical loads are discussed in this paper. The results of analysis may be used in the design for the products.

Keywords: Optimal Design; Composites; Buckling Stress; Matrix Content; Optimal off-Axis.

1. INTRODUCTION

We have tested 300 pieces of composite rectangular plates under simply supported on all sides and uniaxial compression, and get the conclusion that the experimental results coincide with theoretical analysis. Thus, it can be inferred that the buckling theory of anisotropic thin plate is suitable for any type of fiber reinforced composites and various boundary conditions. The major fiber reinforced composite products are of thin-wall structure and its critical load is the base of the designing load in general design. Therefore, the study on critical load of thin plate is meaningful for practical use. With the development of advanced composites, the merits of thin-wall structure products are more obvious. For example, if the plate of carbon fiber reinforced composites is compared with that of hard aluminium in same dimensions, both critical loads in compression are approach, the former weight is only half of the latter^[1]. Composites are designable structure materials. There is an optimal design for the goal of reaching the biggest critical load. This includes three aspects: a. the selection of the optimal matrix content; b. the selection of the optimal off-axis; c. the selection of optimal dimensions and boundary conditions of the plate. The first and second aspects and plate dimensions in the third aspect are discussed in this paper.

2. COMPARISON OF TEST WITH STABILIZATION THEORY OF ORTHOTROPIC RECTANGULAR THIN PLATE IN UNIAXIAL COMPRESSION

The tests are carried with a special fixture made by ourselves for stabilization test of thin plate under compression. Both loading head are metal plates having V shape groove, both the special longitudinal sides supports which may rotate freely make tested plate sides keeping straight. Several methods for determining the critical load have been used, it is shown that Southwell's method is satisfactory for the stabilization of thin plate. Because of the initial deformation of the plate and non-uniformity of its thickness, sometimes the longitudinal wave of the plate buckling deformation is asymmetric. If gages are not set at the place where wave crest appears, test error will be produced. The tested specimens have aspect ratio (i.e. a/b)-1.3, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5, and fiber direction is 0, 90, 45 degree, and plate thickness is 0.5 to 5.5 mm. The fiber volume

of the specimen in longitude and latitude is the same. The comparative tests for compressive elastic modulus of thin composite plates are carried out by using several methods, the experimental results coincide the theoretical predictions. Therefore, we may use experimental values or theoretical predictions when calculating the critical load of the plate. But in optimal design the theoretical predictive formula is used. The experimental results are drawn on Fig. 1 (experimental points are the average of three specimens).

According to tested results, the elastic constants of specimens in longitude and latitude are equal basically, those are $E_1 = E_2 = 20$, $G_{12} = 3.5$ (GPa), $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 0.15$. For 45 degree off-axis specimens, the elastic constants are $E_{45} = 10$, $G_{45} = 8$ (GPa), $\mu_{45} = 0.47$.

When the fibers are arranged in form of cross-ply, the thin plate of fiber reinforced composites can be treated by buckling theory of orthotropic plate, then the critical load of simply supported on four sides rectangular plate in uniaxial compression is as follows[2]

$$N_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{b} \sqrt{D_{11} D_{12}} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \left(\frac{m}{\lambda} \right)^2 + \frac{4 D_{16}}{\sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}} \frac{m}{\lambda} + \frac{2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{\sqrt{D_{11} D_{12}}} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{4 D_{26}}{\sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}} \frac{\lambda}{m} + \frac{D_{22}}{D_{11}} \left(\frac{\lambda}{m} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2.1)$$

Where D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{66} etc. have been presented in mechanics of composite materials. For our specimens, we may take $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$. According to the formula (2.1) and properties mentioned above, the the formula of buckling stress for our specimens under compression can be simplified as

$$\text{in longitude or latitude: } \sigma_{cr} = 2.54 E (t/b)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{in 45 degree off-axis: } \sigma_{cr} = 6.2 E (t/b)^2 \quad (2.3)$$

The longitudinal and latitudinal theoretical results of these plates are drawn on Fig. 1. It is shown that the theoretical values are well in agreement with test results. The theoretical values of 45 degree off-axis plates are higher than those of the longitudinal or latitudinal one. This conclusion is also proved by the experimental results.

From formula (2.2), the suitable range of the buckling stress formula for cross-ply GFRP plate (take the compressive strength of GFRP plate $\sigma_{23} = 200$ MPa) is:

$$b/t > 16 \quad (2.4)$$

Theoretical results, it is shown that for general GFRP thin plates the effect of shear deformation on buckling stress can be not considered. Only when $b/t < 30$, the effect of shear deformation has to be taken into account.

From the compressive stress-strain curve of GFRP along 45 degree off-axis, it is shown that the proportional limit stress is about 60 MPa [3]. The stress-strain curve after proportional limit appears obviously nonlinear. Considering this nonlinearity, the calculating formula of buckling stress is

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_{45} \sqrt{\gamma}}{12 (1 - \mu_{45}^2)} \left[1 + \frac{1}{\gamma} + 2 \mu_{45} + \frac{4 G_{45}}{E_{45}} \right] (t/b) \quad (2.5)$$

Where

$$\gamma = \frac{E_F}{E_{45}}$$

$$E_F = \frac{4 E_{45} E_{45}^1}{(\sqrt{E_{45}} + \sqrt{E_{45}^1})^2}$$

When $b/t < 32$, the compressive buckling stress of GFRP plate along 45 degree off-axis should be calculated by the formula (2.5).

3. SELECTION OF OPTIMAL MATRIX CONTENT

The character of composites is designable. From formula (2.1) it is known that the compressive critical load of plate is in direct proportion to the bending stiffness, while bending stiffness is direct proportion to third power of plate thickness. According to the analysis of composites properties, the elastic modulus of plate is reduced with the increasing of matrix content, but the thickness of plate is increased. Generally, the action of the thickness to bending stiffness is bigger than the modulus. As an example of fiber fabric reinforced composites, its thickness related with the matrix content is as follows:

$$t = \frac{W_F [\rho_m + A (\rho_f - \rho_m)]}{\rho_f \rho_m (1 - A)} \quad (3.1)$$

When the void content C is considered, then

$$t = \frac{[W_F (1 - C) + C t_f \rho_f] [\rho_m + A (\rho_f - \rho_m)]}{\rho_f \rho_m (1 - A)} \quad (3.2)$$

Where W_F is the weight of a unit area of the fabric, t_f is the thickness of the fabric, ρ_f , ρ_m are the densities of the fiber and matrix, respectively. GFRP made by 0.2 mm twill weave cloth, for example, their relations are shown in Fig. 2. For comparison, the relations between the volume content of the fiber, the density of GFRP and the matrix content are also shown in Fig. 2.

From biggest stiffness under condition of equal weight, the optimal matrix content of composite plates can be found. Substituting the formulae of the density and elastic modulus of composites into the stiffness parameter E/ρ^3 , and let the first derivative of E/ρ^3 with respect to A equal zero, then the equation of optimal matrix content for composite thin plate is

$$C_1 A^2 + C_2 A + C_3 = 0 \quad (3.3)$$

Where

$$C_1 = 3 (E_F - E_m) (\rho_f / \rho_m - 1) \frac{2 n_1}{n_1 + n_2} - 3 (\rho_f / \rho_m - 1)^3 E_m$$

$$C_2 = 2 (E_F - E_m) (\rho_f / \rho_m - 1) \frac{n_1}{n_1 + n_2} (3 - \rho_f / \rho_m)$$

$$- 6 (\rho_f / \rho_m - 1)^2 E_m$$

$$C_a = - (E_f - E_{m1}) (2 \rho_f / \rho_{m1} - 3) \frac{n_1}{n_1 + n_2} - 3 (\rho_f / \rho_{m1} - 1) E_{m1}$$

According to the calculation of the formula (3.3), the optimal matrix weight ratio A and fiber volume ratio V_f for several composite plates are listed in Table 1. In the calculation, for the glass fiber, taking E_f = 70 GPa, ρ_f = 2550 kg/m³; for boron fiber, taking E_f = 2000 GPa, ρ_f = 2560 kg/m³; for matrix taking E_{m1} = 3.5 GPa, ρ_{m1} = 1270 kg/m³. For carbon or graphite fiber, because their density has wider variation (1380 - 1700 kg/m³) and they are close to that of matrix, therefore, the optimal matrix content is not found by the formula (3.3). It is shown that for the carbon or graphite fiber reinforced composite plates, the less the matrix content is, the higher compressive critical load will be, if it can satisfy the processing requirement and matrix has impregnated to all interface of the fibers. The n₁, n₂ in the formula (3.3) are the ratio of longitudinal fiber volume to latitudinal one.

Table 1 Optimal matrix content of composite plates

Materials	GFRP				BFRP			
	1:1	4:1	7:1	unidirectional	1:1	4:1	7:1	unidirectional
Matrix weight content A (%)	49.0	42.7	41.9	40.7	33.5	33.2	33.2	33.0
Fiber volume content V _f (%)	34.3	40.2	40.9	42.0	49.8	50.2	50.2	50.4

From Table 1, it is shown that for thin-wall structure product of GFRP, if the compressive critical load is considered as designing load, then the matrix content in GFRP is higher. For balance cross-ply GFRP, the matrix content is 49%, it is the content which is reached in hand lay-up process. For GFRP made using 4:1, 7:1 glass cloth, the optimal matrix content are reduced slightly. This is only for the plate with λ = a/b < √(2 * (D₁₁⁴ / D₂₂)). For different λ, the optimal matrix content is varied, but the variation is not big. Therefore, the data in Table 1 may be applied in product design. For the boron fiber composites having higher modulus, the optimal matrix content is reduced obviously, and the difference between the balance cross-ply and unidirection is very small.

4. SELECTION OF OPTIMAL OFF-AXIS

From Fig. 1 and formulae (2.2) and (2.3), we know that the critical stress of the cross-ply composite plate under compression which loading along 45 degree off-axis to the fiber is higher slightly than that of longitudinal or latitudinal plate. In order to compare the optimal off-axis of the highest critical loads of the composite plates having different dimensions and different fiber ratios, the formula (2.1) may be divided by the critical load of symmetric cross-ply quadrate plate, then

$$\frac{\bar{N}_{cr}}{N_{cr}^1} = \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} \sqrt{\bar{D}_{11} \bar{D}_{22}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{\bar{D}_{11}}{\bar{D}_{22}}} \left(\frac{m}{\lambda} \right) + \frac{2(\bar{D}_{12} + 2\bar{D}_{66})}{\bar{D}_{22}} + \sqrt{\frac{\bar{D}_{22}}{\bar{D}_{11}}} \left(\frac{\lambda}{m} \right) \right] \quad (4.1)$$

Where \bar{D}_{11} , \bar{D}_{22} , \bar{D}_{12} , \bar{D}_{66} represent the bending stiffness, Poisson's stiffness and twist stiffness of plates having off-axis angles, respectively. These can be found from mechanics of composite materials [4]. N_{cr} is the critical load of the quadrature plate.

For 1:1, 4:1, 7:1 GFRP plates, the basic elastic properties are calculated by the optimal matrix content mentioned above. The theoretical results from the formula (4.1) are listed in Table 2 for the different dimensions of the plate. If the matrix content for 4:1 and 7:1 GFRP plate is the same as 1:1 GFRP, then the theoretical results are lower than that in Table 2.

For 1:1 boron fiber composite plates, take $E_1 = E_2 = 116$ GPa, $G = 7$ GPa, $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 0.15$. For the unidirectional boron fiber composite plates with $E_1/E_2 = 10$, take $E_1 = 211$ GPa, $E_2 = 21.1$ GPa, $G = 7.03$ GPa, $\mu_1 = 0.3$, $\mu_2 = 0.03$ [6]. The theoretical results are as shown in Table 3.

From Tables, it can be seen that for symmetric cross-ply (i.e. 1:1) GFRP plate, when $\lambda > 0.8$, the optimal off-axis is 45 degree, while $\lambda = 0.5$, the optimal off-axis is 0 or 90 degree. For 4:1 and 7:1 GFRP plate, the optimal off-axis are varied with λ and the fiber ratio. The optimal off-axis angle are reduced but the critical load are increased with decreasing of λ . The critical load of 7:1 GFRP plate is higher than that of 1:1 GFRP. From Table 3, their similar rule can be seen. The optimal off-axis is not completely the same with reference [6].

5. CONCLUSION

From the research work mentioned above, the following conclusions can be got:

1. The buckling stress calculated by theory of orthotropic plate coincides well with the experimental results. It is shown that our test fixture is reasonable.
2. When the critical load is considered as designing load for thin-wall composite structures, there is an optimal design problem. The optimal matrix contents are varied not only with the constituents properties but with the fiber ratio as well. The optimal matrix content given in this paper can be used for product design.
3. In order to develop the highest critical load of thin-wall structure in compression, the fiber in composites have an optimal off-axis. There are different optimal off-axis for different aspect ratio λ , different fiber properties and different fiber ratio. The optimal off-axis given in this paper can be used for product design.
4. When the specific product is designed, in order to reach a higher bearing capacity of the product, the reasonable aspect ratio must be selected, that is shown in Table 2 and 3.

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Table 2 Optimal off-axis and compressive critical load of the GFRP plate with different aspect ratio

\bar{N}_{cr}	n_1/n_2	λ	m	Direction						Optimal off-axis and \bar{N}_{cr}	
				0°	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°		90°
Critical load ratio	1:1	0.5	1	1.713	1.697	1.665	1.649	1.665	1.697	1.713	0°, 90° 1.713
		0.8	1	1.064	1.082	1.119	1.137	1.119	1.082	1.064	45° 1.137
		1.0	1	1.000	1.022	1.065	1.086	1.065	1.022	1.000	45° 1.086
		1.25	1	1.064	1.082	1.119	1.137	1.119	1.082	1.064	45° 1.137
		1.5	2	1.108	1.124	1.156	1.171	1.156	1.124	1.108	45° 1.171
		2.0	2	1.000	1.022	1.065	1.086	1.065	1.022	1.000	45° 1.086
	2.5	2	1.064	1.082	1.119	1.137	1.119	1.082	1.064	45° 1.137	
	4:1	0.5	1	2.580	2.507	2.280	2.001	1.759	1.604	1.552	0° 2.580
		0.8	1	1.426	1.430	1.418	1.348	1.215	1.078	1.019	18° 1.430
		1.0	1	1.227	1.251	1.286	1.262	1.156	1.025	0.966	33° 1.288
		1.25	1	1.186	1.221	1.283	1.288	1.200	1.077	1.019	38.5° 1.300
		1.5	1	1.263	1.317	1.376	1.394	1.318	1.202	1.147	40.5° 1.400
		2.0	2	1.227	1.251	1.286	1.262	1.156	1.025	0.966	33.5° 1.288
	7:1	0.5	1	2.925	2.810	2.508	2.128	1.785	1.557	1.479	0° 2.925
		0.8	1	1.550	1.552	1.529	1.428	1.247	1.063	0.985	14° 1.553
		1.0	1	1.298	1.327	1.367	1.330	1.186	1.014	0.936	32° 1.368
		1.25	1	1.217	1.262	1.342	1.345	1.226	1.062	0.985	38° 1.369
		1.5	1	1.265	1.318	1.418	1.442	1.338	1.179	1.100	40.5° 1.449
2.0		2	1.298	1.327	1.367	1.330	1.186	1.014	0.937	32.5° 1.368	

Table 3 Optimal off-axis and compressive critical load of the BFRP plate with different aspect ratio

Ncr	n_1/n_2	λ	m	Direction						Optimal off-axis and Ncr	
				0°	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°		90°
Ratio to GFRP quadrate plate	1:1	0.5	1	10.997	10.858	10.581	10.442	10.581	10.858	10.947	0°, 90° 10.997
		1.0	1	5.82	6.161	6.830	7.164	6.830	6.161	5.827	45° 7.164
		1.5	2	6.609	6.872	7.397	7.660	7.397	6.872	6.609	45° 7.660
	unidirectional $E_1/E_2 = 10$	0.5	1	17.385	16.360	13.521	9.839	6.160	3.507	2.543	0° 17.385
		0.8	1	7.497	7.647	7.662	6.750	4.763	2.626	1.700	22° 7.722
		1.0	1	5.326	5.747	6.406	6.147	4.550	2.517	1.616	35° 6.468
		1.25	1	4.074	4.667	5.737	5.895	4.550	2.611	1.700	39° 6.012
		1.5	1	3.552	4.237	5.528	5.912	4.704	2.809	1.903	42° 5.964
		2.0	1	3.472	4.248	5.754	6.360	5.290	3.444	2.544	43° 6.376
	Ratio to BFRP quadrate plate	1:1	0.5	1	1.887	1.863	1.816	1.792	1.816	1.863	1.887
1.0			1	1.000	1.057	1.172	1.230	1.172	1.057	1.000	45° 1.230
1.5			2	1.134	1.179	1.269	1.315	1.269	1.179	1.134	45° 1.315
unidirectional $E_1/E_2 = 10$		0.5	1	2.984	2.808	2.320	1.688	1.057	0.602	0.436	0° 2.984
		0.8	1	1.287	1.312	1.315	1.158	0.817	0.451	0.292	22° 1.325
		1.0	1	0.914	0.986	1.099	1.055	0.781	0.432	0.277	35° 1.110
		1.25	1	0.699	0.801	0.984	1.012	0.781	0.448	0.292	39° 1.032
		1.5	1	0.610	0.727	0.947	1.015	0.807	0.482	0.327	42° 1.023
		2.0	2	0.596	0.729	0.988	1.092	0.908	0.591	0.437	43° 1.094

Fig. 1 Compare test values with theoretical curves of critical stresses

Fig. 2 Correlation of V_f , ρ , t and A